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**IMPACT OF AGRI -TECH STARTUPS ON
PRODUCTIVITY AND EMPLOYMENT – A STUDY IN
NALGONDA DISTRICT OF TELANGANA STATE**

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Abstract

The study aims to know the profile characteristics of Agriculture- Technology(agri-tech) start-up entrepreneurs. It also finds the impact of agri-tech start up on productivity and employment. It enquires the various financial sources to the entrepreneurs and investigates the challenges faced . The study is based on primary data. The study used random sample method to select the agri-tech start up entrepreneurs. Miryalguda Mandal in Nalgonda district of Telangana state was selected for the study due to concentration of agri-tech start- ups.

The study found that 70 percent were postgraduates and 30 percent were Diploma holders; 90 percent were owners and 80 percent were trained agri-tech start up entrepreneurs. The agri-tech start- ups generated employment to 243 persons during the immediate last season. Cooperatives provided loan to 50 percent start- ups and the money lenders provided finance to 35 percent start- up entrepreneurs The study concluded that the main obstacle in using agri-tech start-up was finance. Half of the entrepreneurs' source of finance was cooperatives and money lenders. The study suggested for provision of finance through banks. The new agriculture technology which was developed in the agriculture universities should be introduced to the start-up entrepreneurs to increase productivity and employment.

Keywords: Star-tup entrepreneurs, Agri-tech, Productivity, Employment generation, IOT, Organic farming, Driverless tractors, Bsttery operated tools, Sources of finance

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Introduction:

The global population is projected to reach 10 billion by 2050, there is a pressing need to develop sustainable methods to meet the increasing demand for food, feed, fuel and other industrial products (FAO 2017). To keeping with this growing demand agriculture output must be boosted by 50 percent by 2050 compared to 2012 levels (FAO 2020). In India. the concept of Agri-tech startup was initiated in 2016. The startup India initiative has achieved notable success. By March 2024 there were 1,23,900 startups (DPIIT 2024) Indian Start Ups generated approximately 40,000 new job opportunities, significantly boosting the employment landscape with a total of 1,50,000 to 1,70,000 jobs (Vinayagam, S. 2022). Presently there are 2800 agri-tech startups across various domains including agri-tech, animal husbandry, dairy, fisheries, food processing and organic agriculture. But the agri-tech startups are facing many challenges. The challenges are not limited to productivity and quality of produce but also with building the opportunities for agri- goods in production-consumption continuum (Vijay 2022). These ventures focus on utilizing technology data and innovation to enhance farm productivity, optimize supply chain efficiency, promote sustainability and empower farmers.

The Problem Statement:

Farmers in India confront a host of obstacles in maintaining their livelihoods through agriculture. The shortage of access to advanced technology compounds their challenges leaving them isolated and vulnerable (Bholane, 2023). In India various organizations including the planning commission are actively promoting innovation in the agricultural sector. They are offering grants and investment support at different stages of start-ups, fostering the growth and development of pioneering ideas in the agricultural domain. The agricultural sector, including crops, livestock and fisheries, has witnessed several start-ups commonly named “agri- tech - start- ups”. The agri-start ups are further classified based on their focus like agri tech, animal husbandry, dairy farming, fisheries, food processing, organic agriculture, etc. The present study is concentrated on the agri-tech start ups due to importance of agricultural technology which leads to farm productivity, employment generation and rural development. Agri-tech start ups in Telangana are playing a significant role in boosting agricultural productivity and creating employment opportunities. There is less research on effect of agri-tech start ups on productivity and employment generation this study assumes important and fills the existing gap. This study fills the gap in existing literature.

Objectives ;

1. Know the profile characteristics of Agri-tech startup entrepreneurs
2. Find out the impact on productivity
3. Research the impact on employment generation
4. Investigate the impact of Agri-tech startup on skill development
5. Ascertain the sources of finance to Agri-tech startup entrepreneurs
6. Enquire the challenges faced by the Agri-tech entrepreneurs.

Review of Literature:

Aditya and Sahoo (2022) concluded that the status of agri-tech startups is at their initial stage and it is expected to generate revenues of USD 24 million by the year 2025. They found major constraints faced by farmers, including finance. According to Jadhav and Moharekar (2022) to ensure the success of agri-tech startups the primary focus should be on innovations and collaboration with the startups at the global level. The study by Anjali and Jyothi Yadav (2023) revealed that agri-tech startups in India are driving a transformative shift in the agricultural economy by leveraging technology to bring about significant changes in various aspects of agriculture leading to enhanced value creation and productivity. The tech market for supplying farm input is above expected to be as big as \$ 1 billion. These startups are at the forefront of introducing pioneering solutions to address the constraints encountered by the small and marginal farmers in the agriculture sector. These agri- tech startups have contributed to reducing price of produce generating employment opportunities in rural areas and ensuring timely delivery of produce to consumers. Ashish and Gangwar (August 2025) found that incubation services significantly enhanced the success of agri-tech startups. Demographic variables such as gender, age, education, occupation and household income influence success. The agricultural sector's performance has fluctuated climbing from -0.2 percent in 2014-15 to 6.3 percent in 2016-17, but then decreasing to 2.8 percent in 2019-20. To address challenges such as financing, insurance, coverage and investments in agricultural land and equipment, the development of a vibrant startup environment is crucial (Song, et.al, 2010) According to Bergec and Norman,(2008) business incubators have emerged as critical support structures within this eco. system, providing essential services such as access to funding, mentorship, networking opportunities and infrastructure. These incubators are designed to reduce the risks associated with early stage entrepreneurship by offering a structured environment that promotes growth and development (Mishra and Zachai 2015)

Agri-tech entrepreneurs are leveraging technologies such as IOT (Internet Of Things) Intelligence and big data analytic to optimise farming practices, enhance productivity and ensure sustainability (Al-Mubarak, et.al (2015). Cockayne (2019) revealed that from an economic perspective startups are invaluable for fostering innovation and driving social advancement contributing to enhanced income levels and quality of life in their regions . According to ADB (2020) India has rapidly developed as a hub for startups with over 79000 registered ventures supported by Government initiatives like the” Start Up India Program” launched in 2015. The start- up eco system in India is diverse, encompassing sectors such as Information Technology, health- care,, education and agriculture. Fo example the I|T sector has 8280 recognised startups generating over 98000 jobs while the agriculture sector has 3026 recognised startups creating more than 25000jobs (Startup India2022)

Methodology:

The present study is based on multi stage random sampling technique. In the first stage Telangana state was selected because it was one of the leading states in India with respect to number of agro- tech start- ups. In the second stage Nalgonda district and in the third stage Miryalguda mandal were selected on the same reasons. In the final stage 10 agri-

tech startups were randomly selected from Miryalguda.. A Questionnaire was prepared keeping in view the objectives of study. Two enumerators, having Masters Degree in Economics, were selected for data collection and the questionnaire was fully explained to them. The data were analysed and results drawn.. To know the impact of agri-tech start-ups on productivity the information given by the agri-tech start-ups regarding productivity in the last agricultural season was taken into account. To measure the impact on employment generation, only direct employment created was taken as they could not trace impact on indirect employment generation. Sources of funds to the start-ups were collected for the immediate last season.

Data Analysis and Results:

1(a) Gender and ownership status:

Table (1) shows :Gender and Ownership status of entrepreneurs

Table (1): Gender and Ownership status of entrepreneurs

Gender	Percent	Ownership Status	Percent
Male	90	Proprietor	90
Female	10	Partnership	10
Total	100	Total	100

Source: Primary Data

Table (1) shows that 90 percent were male and 10 percent female among the Agri-tech startup entrepreneurs, revealing that there is lot of scope for female in this sector. Ownership status showed that 90 percent were the proprietors and 10 percent were on partnership basis

1 (b) Annual Turnover and Family size

Table (2) shows the annual turnover and family size of the entrepreneurs

Table (2) Annual Turnover and Family Size of Start-up Entrepreneurs

Annual Turnover	Percent	Family size	Percent
Up to 50 lakh rupees	80	Below 5	20
Above 50 lakh rupees	20	Above 5	80
Total	100	Total	100

Source: Primary Data

Table (2) shows that the annual turnover of 80 percent entrepreneurs was above 50 lakh rupees whereas 20 percent entrepreneurs' annual turnover was below 50 lakh rupees. The family size of 80 percent entrepreneurs was above 5 members whereas it was less than five members for 20 percent entrepreneurs.

1 (c) Education and Training of the entrepreneurs

Table (3) shows the level of education and Training of the entrepreneurs

Table (3): Education and Training of the entrepreneurs

Education	Percent	Training	Percent
Tertiary	70	Trained	80
Diploma	30	Un-trained	20
Total	100	Total	100

Source: Primary Data

Table (3) shows that 70 percent entrepreneurs studied up to tertiary level where as 30 percent studied up to diploma level. 80 percent are trained and 20 percent are untrained. This shows that the start-up entrepreneurs' level of education is satisfactory.

2. Impact on Productivity:

70 percent sample entrepreneurs revealed that introducing technology like precision farming or IOT based services to optimise resources like water, fertiliser leading to higher crop yields and reduced costs. 90 percent entrepreneurs revealed that start-ups promoted organic farming, water conservation and waste management solutions contributing to sustainable and environment friendly agriculture sector. These results are in conformity with Swathi Bhatt (2025) where she pointed out that innovation lies at the heart of productivity increases as new technologies encourage businesses to adopt new operational styles.

3. Impact on Employment generation

Table (4) shows the impact of agri-tech start-ups on employment generation.

Table: (4) Impact of agri-tech start-ups on employment generation

Type of Employment	Number	Percentage
Technical Support	61	25.1
Marketing Sales	61	25.1
Field Operation	74	30.45
Jobs to Young persons	47	19.35
Total	243	100

Source: Primary data

The table shows that during the last agricultural season a total of 243 employment generated. The highest employment generated was related to field operations which was 74 (30.15 %). The employment generation in technical support and marketing sectors was 61 (25.1%). Jobs for young persons were 47 only (19.35%).

4. Source of Finance:

Table (5) shows Sources of Finance to agro-tech start-up entrepreneurs

Tale (5): Sources of Finance

Source of Finance	Percentage
Bank	9.06
Co-operative Society	49.22
Money Lender	35.24
Relatives/Friends	6.48
Total	100

Source: Primary data

The table shows cooperatives and money lenders were playing important role in providing finance to the agri-start-up entrepreneurs. The banks provided finance to 9 percent entrepreneurs only.

5. Challenges faced by the agro-tech start-up entrepreneurs

Table (6) shows challenges faced by the agro-tech start up entrepreneurs

Table (6): Challenges faced by the agri-tech start up Entrepreneurs

Challenges faced by Agri-tech start ups	Percentage
Limited Access to Capital	50
Regulatory hurdles	80
Technological Limitations	20
Market Penetration	30
Resistance from Traditional Players	60

Source: Primary data

The table shows that higher percent start-up entrepreneurs faced challenges related to regulatory hurdles and limited access to capital. Challenges related to technology were the lowest.

Conclusion and Suggestion:

The study concluded that the impact of agri-tech start-up entrepreneurs on agricultural productivity and employment generation was positive. The start-ups promoted organic farming, water conservation and waste management solution contributing to sustainable and environment friendly agriculture sector. Impact on employment generation showed that highest employment generated was related to field operations (74%). The employment generated in technical support and marketing sector was 61 percent respectively. Cooperatives and Money lenders were playing important role in providing finance to 49.22 and 35.24 percent entrepreneurs respectively. It is suggested that the role of banks in providing finance to the start-up entrepreneurs should be increased and the role of money lenders should be reduced.. The challenges related to resistance from traditional players should be reduced.

References:

1. Acs, Z.J. Armington, C & Zhang, T. (2007) The determinants of new firm survivor across regional economies: The role of human capital stock and knowledge spillover. *Papers in Regional Science* 86(3) 367-391
2. Adha, P.S. & Sahoo, S.K. (2022). Agriculture Startups in India. A Revolutionary Idea giving birth to Agripreneur. *International Journal of Innovation Research in Technology*, 687 (April).
3. Aditya, P.S. & Sahoo, S.K. (2022) Agricultural Startups in India. A revolutionary Idea giving birth to Agripreneur. *International Journal of Innovative research in technology*, 687 (April)
4. Al-Mubarak, H.M., Muhammad, A.H. and Busher (2015) Categories of incubator success, A case study of three New York incubator programs. *World Journal of Science, Technology and Sustainable development* 12 (1), 2-12.
5. Anjali & Jyoti Yadao, P. (2023): Role of Agriculture startups in India's land scape, *IJRASET Journal for research in Applied Science and Engineering technology. Issues around data governance in the digital transformation of Agriculture*.
6. Ashish Kumar Isher & Gangwar, V.P. (August, 2025): Can Innovation cultivate growth? A quantitative exploration of Agri-tech Startups and Incubation Impact. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, Vol. 14, article No. 87 (2025).
7. Bergek A, and Norman, C (2008) Incubator best practice. *A framework tech novation*, 28 (1), 20-28.
8. Bholane, K.P. and Patil, V (2023) *Recent Trends and Prospects for agricultural marketing in India*. Pp 1-13.
9. Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT) 2023. *DPIIT Annual Report 2022-23*. Pp 1-224
10. Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) 2017: The future of food and agriculture trends and challenges, *Rome*
11. Food and Agriculture Organisation. The state of food and agriculture overcoming water challenges in agriculture, *Rome. FAO, (2020)*
12. Jadhav, A.P., & Muharekar (2022) Role of Agri-tech startups in India, *56 (1), 2022*.
13. Mishra, C.S., Zachari, R.K. (2015) The theory of entrepreneurship. *Entrepreneur Research Journal* 5 (4), 251-268
14. Song, M., Padaumotsuma .K. , Van Der Bij, Halman (2010) Success factors in new ventures: *A meta analysis Journal of product innovation management*, 27 (1), 7-27. *Va der Bok. J. and Ja;, am. JIM*
15. Startup India (2022). State's startup *Ranking 2022 DPIIT*
16. Vijay Avinash lingam, Sumanth Kumar, Yashwanthi., Kareem Ulla, Shiva, Venkateshwarlu and Srinivasa Rao, C. (2022) *Startup Panorama*. ICAR- National Academy of Agricultural Research Management, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad. Pp 1-56.